

The Sanctuary of Artemis Orthia (Sparta)

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Entry tags: Religious Place, Greek Religions, Greek Cult, Graeco-Roman, Religious Group, Greece, Altar, Sacred Enclosure, Temple

The sanctuary to the goddess Orthia (later conflated with Artemis, according to an inscription from the late first century CE) was one of four sanctuaries built around Sparta in the Iron Age (1100-700 BCE). The sanctuary is located in the village of Limnai, and sits on a flat marshy hollow on the bank of the Eurotas River. The most conspicuous remains today are Roman, in particular an amphitheatre built in the third century CE, built around an earlier temple and altar dating to the sixth century BCE. The excavations in the early 1900s uncovered even earlier phases to this sanctuary, and recent reassessments of the excavation notebooks suggest the earliest structures may date back to the late ninth century BCE. The sanctuary became known from about the fourth century BCE onwards for the harsh rituals performed on the altar at this sanctuary. Both Plato (*Laws*) and Xenophon (*Constitution of the Lacedaemonians*) discuss the training Spartan youths received, enduring harsh trials as part of the system of education known as the *agoge*. The oft-cited flogging of Spartan youths on the altar of Orthia is mentioned Xenophon's *Constitution of the Lakedaimonians* (2.8-9) and elaborated by later authors like Plutarch. Pausanias (3.16.7-11) ties the origins of these violent rites to early conflicts by members of the original four villages of Sparta, who fell to quarrelling and bloodshed over Orthia's altar. The excavations also uncovered a wide array of dedicated objects: ivory plaques and figurines dated primarily to the sixth century, later replaced by bone plaques and other ornaments (including votive flutes); a huge number of lead dedications, in particular lead figurines that reached the tens of thousands by the sixth and fifth centuries BCE; a corpus of clay masks dated to the sixth century representing various characters, including monsters and heroes; and other objects such as terracotta figurines and bronze figurines and jewelry.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 400 CE

Region: Limnai

Region tags: Greece, Laconia, Peloponnese

Location of the remains of the sanctuary of Artemis Orthia in the ancient village of Limnai near the Eurotas River.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dawkins, R.M. (ed.) 1929. *The Sanctuary of Artemis Orthia at Sparta: Excavated and Described by Members of the British School at Athens 1906-1910*. London: Macmillan and Co.
- Source 2: Kaasgaard Falb D.Z. 2009. 'Das Artemis Orthia-Heiligtum in Sparta im 7. Und 6. Jh. V. Chr.', in

Fischer-Hansen, T. and Poulsen, B. (eds), *From Artemis to Diana: The Goddess of Man and Beast* (Copenhagen), 127-52.

Notes: See bibliography at end

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://www3.lib.uchicago.edu/cgi-bin/eos/eos_title.pl?callnum=DF261.S68D3

– Source 1 Description: U Chicago Library's digitization of the 1929 excavation volume

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1906-1910; 1924-1928

Notes: Earlier reports were published annually in the *Annual of the British School at Athens*. The British School team spent another five seasons, from 1924-1928, at the site, but the 1929 volume was based on the original work in 1906-1910.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Sanctuary of Artemis Orthia at Sparta: Excavated and Described by Members of the British School at Athens 1906-1910

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Marsh or bog

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– I don't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

Notes: The earlier (pre-sixth century BCE) altars and temple(s) were decommissioned and buried underneath a layer of sand. A new (sixth-century) temple and altar were built over the sand layer - a small, Doric-style temple. It was refurbished in the Hellenistic period. In the third century CE the Roman amphitheatre was built around the temple.

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

- Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The goddess Orthia. An inscription from the first century CE at this site shows that she was called "Artemis Orthia" by this time. In neighbouring Messenia, Orthia was paired with Artemis by the second century BCE. Based on epigraphic and iconographic evidence, some argue that the fusion between Artemis and Orthia must have been underway by the 6th century BCE.

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are images of a male deity on some of the dedications (e.g., a "Master of Animals" on a few ivory plaques). Jane Carter, in a 1987 article in the *American Journal of Archaeology* ("The Masks of Ortheia"), suggested that a male consort to Orthia may have also been

worshipped at the sanctuary. Pausanias (3.17.1) mentions a temple of Eileithyia close to the sanctuary of Orthia. Two tiles and a die were uncovered in the excavations with variations of Eileithyia's name.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: There are many burials around Limnai going back to the Protogeometric period (see Christesen 2018). In the late seventh century BCE some burials seem to receive ongoing offerings indicative of hero worship (see Pavlides 2010). Sometimes the connection of this worship with specific burials is vague. Whether there is a direct connection with the sanctuary of Orthia is also vague.

Is it a cenotaph:

– I don't know

Reference: P. Christesen. The typology and topography of Spartan burials from the Protogeometric to the Hellenistic period: Rethinking Spartan exceptionalism and the ostensible cessation of adult intramural burials in the Greek world.

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– I don't know

Reference: N. Pavlides. Worshipping heroes: Civic identity and the veneration of the communal dead in Archaic Sparta. (H. Cavanagh , W. G. Cavanagh , J. Roy), Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009. Nottingham: Centre for Spartan and Peloponnesian Studies.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main landscape features would be the marsh and the River Eurotas. Some of the dedications - ivory plaques showing a winged female grasping animals ("Mistress of Animals") and bone carvings - show waterbirds, who were likely seen around the marshes. They may have a connection to death as well, as birds who migrate and return with the seasons.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The third-century CE amphitheatre was built around the temple, with the altar in the middle (arena) of the amphitheatre so that spectators could watch the flogging of boys on the altar.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Notes: The main temple, built in the sixth century BCE, is a simple Doric structure, with an altar out front. There was possibly a surrounding wall to mark out the sanctuary and a cobblestone pavement.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 42.57

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Square meters: 13.5

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Notes: Referring to offerings and decorative elements

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Not sure

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– I don't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Terracotta disc acroteria and antefixes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The cult statue does not survive but is discussed in literature. Pausanias gives this account (from theoi.com): [3.16.9] I will give other evidence that the Orthia in Lacedaemon is the wooden image from the foreigners. Firstly, Astrabacus and Alopeus, sons of Irbus, son of Amphisthenes, son of Amphicles, son of Agis, when they found the image straightway became insane. Secondly, the Spartan Limnatiens, the Cynosurians, and the people of Mesoa and Pitane, while sacrificing to Artemis, fell to quarreling, which led also to bloodshed; many were killed at the altar and the rest died of disease. [3.16.10] Whereat an oracle was delivered to them, that they should stain the altar with human blood. He used to be sacrificed upon whomsoever the lot fell, but Lycurgus changed the custom to a scourging of the lads, and so in this way the altar is stained with human blood. By them stands the priestess, holding the wooden image. Now it is small and light, [3.16.11] but if ever the scourgers spare the lash because of a lad's beauty or high rank, then at once the priestess finds the image grow so heavy that she can hardly carry it. She lays the blame on the scourgers, and says that it is their fault that she is being weighed down. So the image ever since the sacrifices in the Tauric land keeps its fondness for human blood. They call it not only Orthia, but also Lygodesma (Willow-bound), because it was found in a thicket of willows, and the encircling willow made the image stand upright.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Ivory plaques and carvings in soft limestone. Plaques show figures like the "Mistress of Animals" (likely Orthia) and the "Master of Animals"

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Ivory plaques and carvings in soft limestone. Ivory plaques show scenes like Heracles battling the Hydra, Perseus battling the Gorgon, etc.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Ivory plaques and carvings in soft limestone. Images of warriors, individuals holding wreaths, a scene showing departure by ship, among other scenes.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The answers below pertain to the small finds, not architectural decoration - the small finds encompass dedications in lead, ivory, bone, terracotta, and bronze

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Images of sphinxes, gorgons, and griffins

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Images in figurines and small plaques of enthroned female, female between horses, "Mistress of Animals", standing female; sometimes dual females (perhaps priestesses?); "Master of Animals"

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– I don't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Two small ivory plaques show a mirror image of a mourning scene of a deceased male

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– I don't know

Notes: There is recurrent imagery - in particular the winged female, the sphinx, horses, wreaths - these occur particularly in the ivory plaques and lead figurines, but also in terracotta and bronze

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The sanctuary itself is not, but, as mentioned above, there are numerous burials nearby the sanctuary, some of which seem to receive ongoing ritual activity starting in the late seventh century BCE.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: There are two small ivory plaques showing the mourning of a deceased male (mirror image scenes). See Fragkopoulou, F. 2010. 'Sanctuary dedications and the treatment of the dead in Laconia (800-600 BC): The case of Artemis Orthia', in Cavanagh, H., Cavanagh, W.G., and Roy, J. (eds), *Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009* (Nottingham), 83-97.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: At least one burial outside the cemetery, however, shows evidence of sacrifice (tomb BB98 on Stauffert Street). See Pavlides, N. 2010. 'Worshipping heroes: Civic identity and the veneration of the communal dead in Archaic Sparta', in Cavanagh, H., Cavanagh, W.G., and Roy, J. (eds), *Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009* (Nottingham), 551-76.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Outside of the sanctuary there are evidence of graves with grave goods. See Pavlides, N. 2010. 'Worshipping heroes: Civic identity and the veneration of the communal dead in Archaic Sparta', in Cavanagh, H., Cavanagh, W.G., and Roy, J. (eds), *Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese*. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009 (Nottingham), 551-76.. See also Christesen, P. 2018. 'The typology and topography of Spartan burials from the Protogeometric to the Hellenistic period: Rethinking Spartan exceptionalism and the ostensible cessation of adult intramural burials in the Greek world', *BSA* 113, 307-63.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Outside of the sanctuary there are evidence of graves with grave goods. See Pavlides, N. 2010. 'Worshipping heroes: Civic identity and the veneration of the communal dead in Archaic Sparta', in Cavanagh, H., Cavanagh, W.G., and Roy, J. (eds), *Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese*. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009 (Nottingham), 551-76.. See also Christesen, P. 2018. 'The typology and topography of Spartan burials from the Protogeometric to the Hellenistic period: Rethinking Spartan exceptionalism and the ostensible cessation of adult intramural burials in the Greek world', *BSA* 113, 307-63.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the numerous graves around Limnai, it is possible, but hard to say for sure.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: On the question of hero worship around Limnai, see Pavlides, N. 2010. 'Worshipping heroes: Civic identity and the veneration of the communal dead in Archaic Sparta', in Cavanagh, H., Cavanagh, W.G., and Roy, J. (eds), *Honouring the Dead in the Peloponnese*. Proceedings of the conference held at Sparta 23-25 April 2009 (Nottingham), 551-76.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: A stone "dais" inside the temple was suggested by the original excavators to be for purposes of holding the cult statue of Orthia. The cult statue does not survive but is discussed in literature. Pausanias gives this account (from theoi.com): [3.16.9] I will give other evidence that the Orthia in Lacedaemon is the wooden image from the foreigners. Firstly, Astrabacus and Alopecus, sons of Irbus, son of Amphisthenes, son of Amphicles, son of Agis, when they found the image straightway became insane. Secondly, the Spartan Limnatiens, the Cynosurians, and the people of Mesoa and Pitane, while sacrificing to Artemis, fell to quarreling, which led also to bloodshed; many were killed at the altar and the rest died of disease. [3.16.10] Whereat an oracle was delivered to them, that they should stain the altar with human blood. He used to be sacrificed upon whomsoever the lot fell, but Lycurgus changed the custom to a scourging of the lads, and so in this way the altar is stained with human blood. By them stands the priestess, holding the wooden image. Now it is small and light, [3.16.11] but if ever the scourgers spare the lash because of a lad's beauty or high rank, then at once the priestess finds the image grow so heavy that she can hardly carry it. She lays the blame on the scourgers, and says that it is their fault that she is being weighed down. So the image ever since the sacrifices in the Tauric land keeps its fondness for human blood. They call it not only Orthia, but also Lygodesma (Willow-bound), because it was found in a thicket of willows, and the encircling willow made the image stand upright.

Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Notes: The cult statue was inside the temple, as with most Greek cult statues. The extent to which they are easily accessible is debated. See Papalexandrou, N. 2021. *Bronze Monsters and Cultures of Wonder: Griffin Cauldrons in the Preclassical Mediterranean* (Austin). See also Mylonopoulos, I. 2011. 'Divine images behind bars: The semantics of barriers in Greek temples', in Haysom, M. and Wallensten, J. (eds), *Current approaches to religion in ancient Greece* (Stockholm), 269-91.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of food:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Pausanias gives this account (from theoi.com), that suggests that Orthia demanded blood sacrifice of humans, which the legendary lawgiver, Lycurgus, switched to scourging youths on the altar: [3.16.9] I will give other evidence that the Orthia in Lacedaemon is the wooden image from the foreigners. Firstly, Astrabacus and Alopecus, sons of Irbus, son of Amphisthenes, son of Amphicles, son of Agis, when they found the image straightway became insane. Secondly, the Spartan Limnatiens, the Cynosurians, and the people of Mesoa and Pitane, while sacrificing to Artemis, fell to quarreling, which led also to bloodshed; many were killed at the altar and the rest died of disease. [3.16.10] Whereat an oracle was delivered to them, that they should stain the altar with human blood. He used to be sacrificed upon whomsoever the lot fell, but Lycurgus changed the custom to a scourging of the lads, and so in this way the altar is stained with human blood. By them stands the priestess, holding the wooden image. Now it is small and light, [3.16.11] but if ever the scourgers spare the lash because of a lad's beauty or high rank, then at once the priestess finds the image grow so heavy that she can hardly carry it. She lays the blame on the scourgers, and says that it is their fault that she is being weighed down. So the image ever since the sacrifices in the Tauric land keeps its fondness for human blood. They call it not only Orthia, but also Lygodesma (Willow-bound), because it was found in a thicket of willows, and the encircling willow made the image stand upright.

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many dedications in high value materials were found around the altar and

temple - whether Orthia specifically demanded these is unknown. But the practice of dedicating a figurine, weapon, or piece of jewelry is a recognizable custom in ancient Greek worship.

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many dedications in high value materials were found around the altar and temple - whether Orthia specifically demanded these is unknown. But the practice of dedicating a figurine, weapon, or piece of jewelry is a recognizable custom in ancient Greek worship. These could be objects from daily life too.

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: See above notes in "care about or expect offerings"

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: See above notes in "care about or expect offerings"

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely anything dedicated to the god had to remain the god's property. Temples were periodically cleaned as part of the maintenance of the area. See Ekroth, G. 2017. "Don't Throw Any Bones in the Sanctuary!" On the Handling of Sacred Waste in Ancient Greek Cult Places', *Memoirs of the American Academy in Rome, Ritual Matters: Material Remains and Ancient Religion, Supplementary Volume 13*, 33-55.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many Greek deities are invoked in oaths, but to my knowledge Orthia is not.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Animal bones were not saved in the early excavations; presumably animals were offered in sacrifices, in line with other Greek practices.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a difficult question - as mentioned above, Pausanias 3.16.9-11 mentioned that, at some point in the past, humans were sacrificed to Orthia; afterwards, they were scourged on the altar - specifically youths, as part of their training under the Spartan system. The third-century CE Roman amphitheatre was built for people to observe these rituals. See Bonnechere, P. 1993. "Orthia et la flagellation des éphèbes spartiates Un souvenir chimérique de sacrifice humain." *Kernos* 6:11-22. 10.4000/kernos.533.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely there were communal festival days - how mandatory these were is unknown

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There was a substantial reconstruction of the site in the early sixth century BCE - the laying down of a thick layer of sand and the building of a new temple and altar on top. Earlier structures and offerings were sealed underneath the sand layer.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of Laconian-style drinking and dining vessels in the remains at this site. Presumably there were feasting activities alongside animal sacrifices, as at other Greek sanctuaries.

Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

–specify: Exact frequency unknown. Various athletic and choral contests were associated with this site in summer festival known as the Gymnopaediae (Petterson 1992, 52-56; Kennell 1995, 75; Flower 2018, 439-40). This festival was in some way connected to Orthia, based on inscriptions linking worship of Orthia to this festival (Rose 1929, 406).

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–Only initiates

–Elites

–Only locals

Notes: Sparta maintained strict divisions between Spartan citizens (the homioi), non-citizens

(the perioikoi), and the enslaved population (the helotai)

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
– Elites
– Non-elites
– Religious professionals
Notes: Unknown, but presumably

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

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